

Influence of Ionic Strength on the Rate of Alkaline Fading of Brilliant Green

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The effect of neutral salts on the velocity of reactions in solutions has been a subject of study of a number of workers (Long *et al.*, *J. Phys. Coll. Chem.*, 1951, **55**, 813, 829; La Mer, *Chem. Rev.*, 1932, **10**, 179). The study of the above at constant and varied ionic strengths is useful for elucidation of the mechanism of, especially, the charged and uncharged nature of the reacting species involved in the reaction. The mathematical formulation of the salt effects has been developed by Bronsted (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1925, **115**, 337), Bjerrum (*ibid.*, 1924, **108**, 82; 1925, **118**, 25), and Christiansen (*ibid.*, 1924, **113**, 35). The present note reports the application of these equations to the kinetic studies of the decomposition of brilliant green (B.G.), viz., 4,4'-bis-diethylaminotriphenylmethyl sulphate, in alkali solution, to carbinol, on which no data exist in the literature.

B. G. of B. D. H. quality was purified according to the methods described elsewhere (Lewis *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, **64**, 1774). KNO_3 used as the neutral salt was a B.D.H. AnalaR reagent. The reaction was followed spectrophotometrically by observing the optical density at various time intervals. Spectrophotometric measurements were carried out using 10 mm corex cells on a Beckman spectrophotometer, model DU, which was provided with a dual thermospacer set for temperature control. All the kinetic studies reported in this communication were carried out at $25^\circ \pm 0.05^\circ$.

Preliminary experiments showed that B.G. was adsorbed at the glass surface (if kept for more than 10 minutes), thus reducing the effective concentration of the dye. This appeared significant because of the low concentration of the substance used. Studies at higher concentrations were not possible on account of the precipitation of carbinol. The reaction was therefore carried out in wax-coated glass vessels; aliquots of the reaction mixtures were drawn out at desired intervals for spectrophotometric estimation of B.G., which showed absorption maximum at 625 μ , with an extinction coefficient 8.00×10^4 litre mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹. The velocity constant of the reaction was obtained by

$$k' = \frac{2.303 (\Delta \log C_{\text{B.G.}}) \text{ litres}}{(\Delta T) (C_{\text{OH}^-}) \text{ mole. min.}}$$

The effect of ionic strength (μ) on k' was studied by adding increasing quantities of KNO_3 . These data are shown in Fig. 1. It is interesting to note that k' varied markedly with μ . The following equation elucidates the influence of μ on k' :

$$\ln k' = \ln k'_0 + 2A Z_A Z_B \sqrt{\mu} \quad (i)$$

According to eq. (i), k' is a linear function of $\sqrt{\mu}$. It is seen from Fig. 1, curve 1, that eq. (i) is applicable only for low values of μ . At higher values of μ , the points fall away

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FIG. 1

from the linear plot. This deviation from eq. (i) is attributed to the inaccurate values of activity coefficients computed from the Debye-Hückel equation. Applying the modified Debye-Hückel equation for reaction rates (Guntelberg, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1926, 123, 243), we get:

$$\ln k' = \ln k_0' + \frac{2A Z_A Z_B \sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} \quad \dots \quad (ii)$$

which requires a linear plot between k' and $\sqrt{\mu}/(1 + \sqrt{\mu})$. Suggestively enough, eq. (ii) is valid over a wide range of μ (see Fig. 1, curve 2). The data in Fig. 1 (curve 2) give a value of 38.90 litre mole⁻¹ min⁻¹ for velocity constant at zero ionic strength (k_0') and a value of -1.2 for $Z_A Z_B$, suggesting thereby that the reaction involves two species with unit charges of opposite sign.

Thanks are due to Prof. S. N. Gundu Rao, Director, National Sugar Institute, for his kind interest and to the Scientific Research Committee, U.P. for a grant to one of them (S. S. K.).